

plants of the five ages could be simultaneously infested with insects. Each pot was a replication and treatments were replicated 10 times. Before larval infestation, tillers were thinned to 12/pot and 10 first-instar larvae were placed one on each. Two tillers were uninfested. Plants were placed in a 20- × 100-cm mylar film cage. YSB adults were collected and counted when they emerged. Percentage survival was determined:

$$\frac{\text{No. of adults}}{\text{No. of larvae used to infest the plant}} \times 100$$

Survival on IR46 was lowest at early tillering and panicle initiation, and highest at booting (see table). Survival

Survival of 1st-instar YSB larva to the adult stage on medium-duration IR46 and early-maturing IR60 at different plant growth stages, IRRI.

Variety	Growth duration (d)	Survival ^a (%)				
		Early tillering	Maximum tillering	Panicle initiation	Booting	Flowering
IR46	130	44 c	66 b	35 c	85 a	60 b
IR60	110	73 a	43 c	55 b	73 a	70 a

^a In a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

was intermediate at maximum tillering and flowering. Survival on IR60 was lowest at maximum tillering and panicle initiation and equally high at early tillering, booting, and flowering. Results indicate that the high level of resistance

at IR46 panicle initiation is at least partially due to low larval survival. The reason for the different responses of the two varieties to YSB was not determined. □

Effect of slow-release N fertilizers on stem borer (SB) and sheath rot (ShR) incidence and on rice grain yield

G. Alagarsamy, M. Velusamy, S. Rajagopalan, and S. Palanisamy, Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamudram, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India

We studied the effect of slow release N fertilizers on SB and ShR incidence and grain yield of IR20 in 1983-84.

SB and ShR incidence was significantly lower with neem cake-coated urea at both

Effect of slow-release N fertilizers on SB and ShR incidence and rice grain yield,^a Tirunelveli, India.

N source	75 kg N/ha			100 kg N/ha		
	SB (% white heads)	ShR-infected tillers (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	SB (% white-heads)	ShR-infected tillers (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Prilled urea	23 c	41 b	1.2 a	21 b	50 c	1.2 a
Neem cake-coated urea at 20%	6 a	31 a	1.5 a	5 a	33 a	1.5 a
Coaltar-coated urea at 1%	14 b	38 b	1.4 a	17 b	40 b	1.5 a
Urea supergranules	16 b	40 b	1.3 a	17 b	42 b	1.3 a

^a In a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

N levels (see table). Differences in grain yield were not statistically significant.

Heavy rain (500 mm during flowering and maturity stages) reduced grain yield. □

Preventing tungro (RTV) by applying insecticides to control green leafhopper (GLH) in Bangladesh

M. M. Rahman, M. A. Nahar, and S. A. Miah, Plant Pathology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

We tested two insecticide treatments for control of GLH *Nephotettix virescens* and RTV. Carbofuran 3G at 3 kg ai/ha was incorporated in the seedbed before planting seeds, or diazinon 60 EC at 0.6 litre ai/ha was sprayed on seedlings 10 and 20 d after sowing.

In the seedbed, 21-d-old seedlings were inoculated with RTV viruliferous GLH for 4 d. The seedlings were transplanted in 14 treatment plots, each with

RTV infection on TN1 plants treated with carbofuran and diazinon at different growth stages, Joydebpur, Bangladesh.^a

Seedbed treatment	Treatment in transplanted plot			Hills ^b (no.) showing RTV symptoms	
	Land preparation	Max tillering	Panicle initiation	%	Severity ^c
None ^d	-	-	-	30.3 bc	4.3 abc
None	-	-	-	50.8 d	6.3 c
C	-	-	-	27.8 bc	4.3 abc
C	C	-	-	14.0 a	3.0 a
C	C	C	-	15.0 a	3.7 ab
C	C	C	C	8.7 a	3.0 a
None ^d	C	C	C	10.0 a	3.7 ab
None	C	C	C	19.9 abc	3.0 a
D-60	-	-	-	58.6 d	5.7 bc
D-60	D-10	-	-	53.9 bc	5.7 bc
D-60	D-10	D-10	-	31.3 bc	3.7 bc
D-60	D-10	D-10	D-10	53.2 bc	4.3 abc
None ^d	D-10	D-10	D-10	12.0 ab	3.7 ab
None	D-10	D-10	D-10	26.6 abc	3.7 ab

^a A dash (-) means no insecticide was applied. C = carbofuran, D-60 = diazinon 60 EC, D-10 = diazinon 10G. ^b Means of 3 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. ^c Rated by the 1976 Standard evaluation system for rice. ^d Not inoculated with RTV.

3 replications (see table). In the transplanted field, either carbofuran 3G at 0.681 kg ai/ha or diazinon 10G at 1.7 kg ai/ha was incorporated at final land preparation, and broadcast at maximum

tillering and panicle initiation. RTV infection was visually recorded at 70 d after transplanting.

Disease score (percentage and severity) was significantly lower in

carbofuran-treated plots than in diazinon-treated ones. It was lowest when carbofuran was applied in the seedbed and in transplanted plots up to panicle initiation. □

Mass rearing of *Nephotettix malayanus*

H. S. Kim, E. A. Heinrichs, and H. R. Rapusas, IRRI

Mass rearing techniques for the green leafhoppers *N. virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, and *N. cincticeps* have been successfully developed. However, no mass rearing technique has been developed for *N. malayanus*. Tests to select a host plant for *N. malayanus* rearing identified the weed *Leersia hexandra* as the most favorable. We developed a rearing procedure using *L. hexandra* (see fire).

L. hexandra cuttings were prepared by cutting 15-cm side shoots and transplanting them in pots at 10 cuttings/spot. Plants were fertilized with ammonium sulfate at 7 d after transplanting (DT). At 10 DT, 6 pots were placed in the oviposition cage. To start the culture, 100 field-collected females and 100 males were placed in the oviposition cage with the *L. hexandra* plants.

The 6 pots infested with eggs were transferred into the rearing cage and replaced with 6 new potted *L. hexandra* plants at 3 d-intervals. Eggs in the leaf sheaths of *L. hexandra* hatched in 8-10 d. Nymphs reached the 2d and 3d instar in 11-16 d, 4th and 5th in 17-21 d, and adulthood in 22-25 d. Fresh *L. hexandra* plants were placed in the cage each week. About 2,000-3,000 *N. malayanus* individuals can be produced in each generation with 1 oviposition cage and 1 rearing cage. Insects are maintained in the rearing cage until they are needed for varietal screening, insecticide screening,

N. malayanus rearing procedure and use of reared insects, IRRI.

studies on resistance mechanisms and tungro virus infection, or to maintain the

culture by transferring adults to the oviposition cage. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.